

Vernacular Histories and History 2 : Configuring *Madalapanji* of Odisha

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Preface

The present study examined the most popular vernacular *Madalapanji* the chronicle of Jagannath temple in the context of Odisha. Here attempt has been made to understand the complex socio-cultural history of Odisha through vernacular texts. These texts are very unique which provides us continuous political narratives to look at the precolonial past through very different way. These texts were not considered as historical sources for many colonial, national and other historians, but these are very significant to look at the fascinating aspects of regional history of Odisha. Thus, effort has been made to look the history-2 through the pure vernacular like *Madalapanji*.

Keywords- *Vernacular histories, History-2, Madalapanji, Itihasa-Purana Tradition, Rajabhoga Itihasa.*

Introduction

One of the utmost and inalienable question, was there any history writing in Odisha before British colonial intervention ? The old and palpable answer of this question will be 'no'. This question and answer mostly carried over the colonial times. According to the old answer to the question is that the proper historical writing came to Odisha, in the form of the court chronicles of the Islamic rulers. From the days of Delhi sultanate these were written in Persian and followed the character of Indo-Persian historiography. These writing undoubtedly derive their conventions from Arabic, Persian and Turkish histories, and therefore brought many historical writings unknown to Odisha. In other

hand the genre for recording the past through temple chronicles like *Madalapanji*, *Charita* and *Vamsavalis* were not considered historical. According to academic historians these texts were mythical rather than historical. Though these texts contain kernel of narratives about historical events and characters, the convention of reading those texts do not allow us to tell historical from the mythological. So, the records like *Madalapanji* were merely accidentally historical and not self-consciously so. The huge gap of sources between the existence of mass illiterates and the few court centric chronicles is a problem which the existing historiography trends both 'traditional' and 'alternative' are yet to grapple with. A vast range of vernacular texts provides the opportunity to fill the gaps, but also tends to become the 'alternative'

against the already existing ‘master narrative’¹. Careful readings reveal distinctly indigenous historical narratives. These narratives may be embedded within non-historical literary genres, such as poems, ballads and works within the *Itihasa-Purana* tradition, but are marked by discursive signs that allow them to be recognized as historical.

What is Vernacular history ?

The language or dialect spoken by the ordinary people in a particular country or region is known as vernacular. So, in a layman language history produced in the vernacular is vernacular history. But that would be an inaccurate conclusion. In looking for its difference with the colonial modern, shapes and forms we can classify vernacular histories into three categories.

Category 1

Though written in vernaculars but their authority is derived almost entirely from western practices, communicated through education in the English language. These historical writings are humanistic, scientific and rational and methods of writings based on certain sources, scrupulously followed the modern academic practice of western historiography. So, this kind of colonial and post-colonial writings are not appropriate to ascertain vernacular history².

Category 2

There also emerged a plethora of historical writings that might be called a mixture or hybrid. This kind of histories reveal few traces of their vernacular origins. Instead of making its difference from the authorized forms of colonial of postcolonial modernity, this body of writing wanted fully to participate in the formation of

modernity. This kind of vernacular histories were produced in between 18th and 19th century and can be compared to the academic histories.

Category 3

Those histories written in pre-colonial and colonial time and did not follow western academic practices and drawn from the *Itihasa-Purana* traditions, especially the Ramayana-Mahabharata in which particular places, peoples and rulers may have been mentioned. These writings produced in the literature and chronicles like *Madalapanji*, *Rajavamshavalis*, *karanam*, *bakhar* and *buranji* etc. marked a great sense of historical writings which is now called as the ‘Vernacular History.’

What is History-2?

Two types of history have arisen with the spread of capitalism and the emergence of the modern world: “History 1,” that is a past posited by capital as part of its precondition, and “History (or Histories) 2,³” which do not belong to the life process of capital, which may not be subsumed in the narrative of its progress, yet live in intimate and plural relationships with it, and which allow us to make room for human diversity and the politics of belonging. History 1 as purely analytical whereas History 2 beckons “more effective narratives of human belonging”. In other words, “politics of human diversity” and argues that various History 2s continuously modify History 1. History 2 lies in the ability to create room for incorporating the history of human subjective experiences into the history of capital and vice-versa. History 1 is Euro centric and based upon western model of capital, modernity, scientific and rational outlook. History 1 looks Vernacular history through single dimension of Eurocentric model. But history 2 is based upon linear time

and heterogeneous sphere. While history 1 rejects many vernacular sources due to their inclination towards mythic and religion, History 2 look these vernacular texts with their time value and message embodied for society and humanity.

Madalapanji

Except Kalhan's *Rajatarangini* (Chronicle of Kashmiri Kings), datable to 12th Century A.D., there is no other text in Sanskrit which may be regarded as historical literature. In this context the *Madalapanji*, the palm-leaf Odia chronicle of the Jagannath temple of Puri is of immense importance. It gives the traditional history of Odisha in relation to Jagannath temple from early times to the second decade of 19th Century. *Madalapanji* has played an important role in shaping the history of Odisha by some historians. While writing Odia history, historians like W.W.Hunter and Andrew Stirling considered the facts in *Madalapanji* as base. The *Madalapanji* was traditionally written on a year-to-year basis. On *Vijaya-Dashami* day, the *Karanas* (official history writers of Puri and an Odia Hindu caste) involved in keeping the chronicle. This ritual is cited as a proof that the tradition of keeping this chronicle began with Odia king *Anantavarman Chodaganga Dev* himself. Though the actual date of starting of *Panjis* is not known, but it is believed that it might be started from 12th century AD. The book is a classic and literary master piece of the Odia language first order. It can be compared with *Rajvansham* of Sri Lanka, *Rajtarangini* of Kashmir and *Burunji* of Assam. The earliest use of prose can be found in the *Madalapanji* or the Palm-leaf Chronicles of the Jagannath temple at Puri, which date back to the 12th century. According to the tradition, *Chodaganga* created 24 families of *Karanas* to preserve the temple records. Of these, five were

entrusted with the writing and preservation of the *Madalapanji*. They are:

Panjia Karan—preserves the *Madalapanji*

Tadau Karan—writes the *Madalapanji*

Deula Karan—enforces the *Madalapanji*

Kotha Karan—the main compiler

Baithi Karan – assistant

The *Madalapanji* mostly deals with the history of the kings of Odisha (Rajabhoga Itihasa) from the Satyayuga to the modern time. According to R.P. Chanda The *Madalapanji* comprises all classes of chronicles such as lists of articles in Store, routine of ceremonies, copies of the orders of the Gajapati Maharajas of Odisha⁴. The *Rajabhoga Itihasa*, written in Odia, was edited by late Prof. Arta Ballabha Mohanty in 1940 and published by Utkal University in 1969⁵. The Sanskrit version of this text, *Katakarajavamsavali*, was edited by G.C. Tripathy and H. Kulke⁶. The Bengali version of the *Madalapanji*, entitled *Purusottama Chandrika*, was published by Bhabani Charan Bandopadhyaya in 1847. The Telugu version of *Madalapanji* entitled *Jagannath Kaifiyat* is conserved in the Madras Oriental Library. Similarly, a version of this text entitled *Odradesa Rajavamsavali* was edited by K.C. Mishra in 1983⁷.

The *Madalapanji* is not ordinary Vamsavali of kings. The focus of the Panji is Jagannath Who is mentioned as the lord of Odisha. The text emphasizes the continuous presence of Jagannath in the Kshetra. The construction of the temple, institution of *Chhatis Niyoga*, the pilgrimage of Kings and saints to *Purushottama Kshetra* and their devotion to Jagannath and reflected in this text.

The *Madalapanji* refers to several places and religious centres of Odisha. The *Desa Khanja* section of *Madalapanji*, records land grants to Jagannath temple and sources of the property of Jagannath. An account of it is given in Jagannath Sthalavrttantam, a Telegu text in the Mackenzie collection of Madras Oriental library.

The *Madalapanji* has arranged the dynasties of Odisha in chronological sequence such as, the *Kesharis*, the *Gangas*, The *Gajapatis*, The *Bhois* and *Khurda raja*. The Afghans, the Mughals and the British are also mentioned in correct sequence.

The text not only records political history but also economic condition of the people, cyclones, famines, scarcity, deluges, attacks by outsiders and change of dynasties. *Jagannath Sthalavrttantam* has been translated into English by S.N. Rajguru and published by Sri Jagannath Sanskrit University, Puri. There are minor differences in versions depending upon whose custody it was found. Because the compilation of this text was the work of many hands. In many cases this text embellished with legends and this makes it less reliable. But these texts often give voice to identities and aspirations that find no place within the institutional structures of Professional history writing. By celebrating the living memory of the community, they question the state-centric logic of modern historiography. Even though the domain of the vernacular altogether most exaggerated and dramatic, effective histories is being made in the vernacular.⁸

Bibliography :

1. Sheldon Pollock, Sanskrit Literary Culture from the Inside Out, *Literary Cultures in History: Reconstructions from South Asia*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 2003.
2. Raziuddin Aquil, Partha Chatterjee, *history in the vernacular*, Delhi, Permanent Black, 2010.

3. Dipesh Chakrabarty, *Provincilizing Europe: Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference*, Princeton University Press, 2008
4. R.P. Chanda, “note from the Madalapanji”, *Journal of Bengal Orissa research society*, 1927, Vol. XIII, p.10
5. A.B. Mohanty, *Madalapanji, Rajabhoga Itihasa*, Prachi edition. 1940, 2nd edition, Utkal University, 1969.
6. G.C. Tripathy, H. Kulke (ed), *Katakaraja vamsavali*, Allahabad, 1987.
7. K.C. Mishra (ed). *Odradesa Rajavamsavali*, BBSR, 1983.

References :

1. Sheldon Pollock, Sanskrit Literary Culture from the Inside Out, *Literary Cultures in History: Reconstructions from South Asia*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 2003.
2. Raziuddin Aquil, Partha Chatterjee, *history in the vernacular*, Delhi, Permanent Black, 2010.
3. Dipesh Chakrabarty, *Provincilizing Europe: Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference*, Princeton University Press, 2008.
4. R.P. Chanda, “note from the Madalapanji”, *Journal of Bengal Orissa research society*, 1927, Vol. XIII, p.10
5. A.B. Mohanty, *Madalapanji, Rajabhoga Itihasa*, Prachi edition. 1940, 2nd edition, Utkal university, 1969.
6. G.C. Tripathy, H. Kulke (ed), *Katakaraja vamsavali*, Allahabad, 1987.
7. K.C. Mishra (ed). *Odradesa Rajavamsavali*, Bhubaneswar, 1983.
8. Raziuddin Aquil, Partha Chatterjee, *history in the vernacular*, Delhi, Permanent Black, 2010.

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